

EPOXY RESIN-THERMOPLASTIC BLENDS CURED BY IONISING RADIATION. STRUCTURE/PROPERTIES RELATIONSHIPS

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SUMMARY

Radiation curing of an epoxy resin based blend is carried out in order to produce polymer matrices for high-performance composites. A suitable choice of both curing process and formulation parameters allows to irradiate at about 60°C. Moreover hydrothermal ageing is performed on cured materials and their properties have been evaluated.

Keywords: radiation curing, toughened epoxy resins, hydrothermal ageing

INTRODUCTION

Radiation processing is proposed as an alternative methodology to cure composite materials for aerospace and advanced automotive applications.

With respect to thermal curing, the most attractive aspect of this process lies in the fact that it does not need thermal activation, so that it can be performed near room temperature. This brings several positive consequences such as energy costs saving, the use of low cost moulds and the improvement of mechanical properties of the cured materials due to the reduced residual thermal stresses. Furthermore radiation curing, conversely to thermal curing, does not need the use of toxic hardeners but only the presence of a very small quantity of acidic salt as initiator. This fact, together to the reduced volatile emission caused by the use of low temperatures, makes radiation curing an environmentally friendly process. Other advantages are the great flexibility of the process and the short curing times [1-3].

On the other hand during radiation curing the temperature of the system can undergo to a significant increase due to the occurring of both exothermic polymerization reactions and radiation absorption. The extent of this phenomenon depends, for fixed components and geometry of the mould, on the component ratio and on the rate by which the energy is provided to the sample, that is the irradiation dose rate of the process [4-6]. The occurrence of a not expected heating causes a simultaneous thermal curing during irradiation, invalidating the beneficial effects coming out from a not thermally activated process.

It is well known that epoxy resins matrices have a high stiffness, but generally suffers from poor fracture toughness [7-9]. Considering that for advanced applications they are required to show at the same time high toughness, high thermal resistance (high T_g) and high stiffness, the toughening of these matrices, without worsening the other properties,

is a crucial step. The most used toughening method consists of the introduction of engineering thermoplastics, having both high elastic modulus and high T_g. Starting from an “homogeneous” blend, the occurring of separation phase phenomena between the resin and the thermoplastic gives rise to a specific morphology whose characteristics determine the distribution of stresses in the material and hence its fracture mechanisms [10,11]. To this regard, the study of the morphological structure of these systems is essential and considering that the morphology results not only from the components nature and their ratio, but also from the process, it is evident that a great effort has to be devoted to the individuation of the optimal choice of all the parameters governing the process. It is well known from literature, concerning thermally cured epoxy systems, that co-continuous type morphology at a nano-micro metric scale is very effective in improving fracture toughness, but the design of a material having specific mechanical features, tailored for specific applications, is not easy to perform, especially when several parameters are introduced in the process, such as in the case of radiation curing [12].

In addition to this problematic it has to be considered that all the properties of the cured materials, whatever the curing process used, should remain acceptable during service. In fact for structural applications a very important issue is the long-term performance of such materials under exposure to various environmental conditions during their operating life. Thermal excursion and water absorption are the most common and very critical environmental conditions, with respect to ageing, mainly for aeronautic applications. It is well recognized that generally polymer matrix composites suffer substantial losses in their properties under cyclic thermal excursions and moisture/solvents absorption and desorption [13-15].

The magnitude of ageing effects is strongly related to the micro/nano structure of the matrix, since moisture/solvents absorption is governed by diffusive processes [16]. For these reasons the interpretation of ageing phenomena is strongly related to a systematic and careful study of the morphological structure of the matrix network realized in the material.

For thermally cured materials several ageing studies are reported in literature, where effects of hydrothermal treatment are investigated, while there are not similar extended studies for radiation cured materials.

In this work blends of a difunctional epoxy resin and a commercial polyethersulfone are e-beam cured at about 60°C in the presence of a strong acid salt as initiator. Some of the cured samples have been further subjected to a post-irradiation thermal curing in order to complete the cure process. Both radiation cured and thermally post cured materials were hydrothermally aged. The materials have been characterized through morphological, mechanical and thermal investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL

The epoxy resin was Bis(4-glycidylphenoxy)methane (DGEBA) supplied by Aldrich. The thermoplastic toughening agent was a commercial polyether sulfone (PES), Mw 25000, and the initiator was an onium salt, Cumyltolylidonium tetra(pentafluorophenyl) borate, supplied by Rhodia Silicones.

Blends were prepared mixing the thermoplastic with the epoxy resin at 130°C for 2 hours. Then, after cooling at 60°C, the initiator was added. Systems with 10 phr of

thermoplastic and with 0.5 phr of salt were prepared. E-beam irradiation has been carried out in closed steel moulds (150x150x4mm) at the ISOF-CNR laboratory in Bologna with the 12-MeV Vickers type linear accelerator [17]. The irradiation dose was 80 kGy and the dose rate 70 kGy/h.. During irradiation the temperature inside the sample has been recorded through a thermo resistor connected to a computer. Post irradiation thermal curing has been carried out at 120°C for 2 hours.

The accelerated hydrothermal ageing has been performed on both irradiated and post-irradiation thermally cured samples, dipping them in distilled water at 70°C. The water absorption was monitored by periodical weighting and samples were characterised after reaching the equilibrium conditions, i.e. after about 1500 hours.

Thermal behaviour has been studied by dynamic mechanical thermal analysis (DMTA) through a Rheometrics DMTA V apparatus, equipped with a single cantilever bending fixture, in a temperature sweep mode in the 25-250 °C range at a heating rate of 2°C /min. The strain level was set at 0.02% and the frequency was 1.8 Hz. Storage modulus (E') and loss factor ($\tan\delta$) vs temperature were recorded.

The morphology of the cured materials has been analysed by a scanning electron microscopy. The surfaces have been etched in super-acid solution and then gold coated.

The mechanical tests were performed by an Instron 3367 having a loading cell of 1 KN using the ASTM D5045 96 standard.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The monitoring of the temperature in the sample during irradiation is crucial because, as it has been said above, its eventual unexpected heating due to both polymerization reactions and energy absorption could compromise its final properties, besides invalidate the advantages of a “cold” process [4,11]. Moreover the thermal profile related to the process affects either the kinetics of the curing reactions or the phase separation mechanisms eventually occurred. For these reasons the temperature profile during irradiation is an important reference in order to compare different systems.

In this work irradiation of samples has been carried out with a thermal profile of about 60°C. This condition has been realized, for a fixed thermoplastic content and for a fixed geometry, using an optimal percentage of initiator and a suitable dose rate of the process. In particular, starting from room temperature, during irradiation the temperature of the sample gradually increases up to a plateau value. The use of a mild temperature process causes on the materials vitrification effects, since the T_g of the cured portions soon becomes near the cure temperature and the process is controlled by the diffusion of the reactive species among them. For these reasons after irradiation the samples have been also thermally post cured in order to complete curing reactions, but conversely to the real thermal curing this process is performed on already solid samples and hence out of the mould, without inducing residual thermal stresses in the final materials. Moreover this thermal treatment is relatively short with respect to the traditional thermal curing methods.

In Fig.1 DMTA loss tangent curves are reported. For only irradiated sample, the curve presents two relaxation peaks, corresponding to the glass transitions of clusters with different network densities. This behaviour is related to the before discussed vitrification phenomena occurring during irradiation at low temperature. In particular

the second peak can be the result of the relaxation of both high crosslinked portions of materials obtained by irradiation and low crosslinked parts evolved toward higher crosslinking during the thermal treatment of the DMTA analysis itself. It is reasonable that a thermal treatment after irradiation, at a temperature value sufficiently high to overcome vitrification effects (between the two relaxations), is able to make the system more “homogeneous” from the crosslinking degree point of view. The $\tan\delta$ curve for such condition, reported in the same figure, shows in fact only one peak that is at a temperature value almost correspondent to the second peak of the only irradiated system.

Fig. 1 Loss factor as function of the temperature. a) irradiated; b) irradiated and thermally post cured; c) irradiated and aged; d) irradiated, thermally post cured and aged

The water absorption measure, reported in Fig. 2, shows that the percent weight increase at equilibrium (1500 hours) is 3.4 and 2 for only irradiated and post irradiation thermally cured systems respectively. This effect is clearly related to the different crosslink density, as already shown by DMTA tests, but also to the possible occurrence of physical ageing that, causing a reduction of the free volume, has the effect of decreasing both the diffusion rate and the uptake capability of water [13, 18].

After hydrothermal ageing the presence of only one peak in the $\tan\delta$ curves, reported in Fig.1, is observed either for irradiated or post irradiation thermally treated systems. For the only irradiated sample the disappearance of the low temperature relaxation peak can be attributed to the thermal curing during ageing, also facilitated by the effect of plasticization due to the absorbed water. The $\tan\delta$ peak is at a temperature value intermediate between the two peaks of the correspondent not aged sample.

In the post irradiation thermally treated sample always only one relaxation peak is observed, but at higher temperature. This phenomenon can be related to the plasticization due to the absorbed water, without any post irradiation thermal curing effect. It is worth to note that the glass transition temperature of this last material does not dramatically decrease after hydrothermal.

Fig. 2 Water absorption curves for toughened samples.

Toughness measurements and SEM analysis, here not reported, relate K_{IC} values and morphology to both processing conditions and ageing procedures. A general decrease of K_{IC} is observed after thermal treatment and hydrothermal ageing. These results can be related to the increase of crosslinking due to post irradiation thermal curing and to micro-scale phase separation phenomena due to ageing effects evidenced by SEM.

CONCLUSIONS

Radiation curing of an epoxy-thermoplastic blend has been carried out with a mild temperature profile, through the choice of an optimal value of the process rate.

Dynamic mechanical thermal analysis of the irradiated sample evidences the formation of clusters at different crosslinking densities caused by vitrification effects. The use of a post irradiation thermal treatment, out of the mould, allows to obtain a more “homogeneous” structure showing only one relaxation at high temperature.

The accelerated hydrothermal ageing on the irradiated sample causes a significant change in the $\tan\delta$ curve with a “homogenization” of the crosslinking density due to both plasticization and thermal curing effects, while for the post irradiation thermally cured sample a not dramatic decrease of T_g is observed, justified by its lower water absorption.

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